

DEVELOPING A MANAGEMENT MODEL FOR LABORATORY MADRASAH ALIYAH – CASE STUDY IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

Aim: Islamic religious schools in Indonesia urgently require laboratory schools to enhance their educational offerings. These laboratory schools, *Madrasah Aliyah* (MA) or Islamic senior high schools, currently suffer from suboptimal management. **Methods and Materials:** This study aims to analyze the existing management model of Laboratory *Madrasah Aliyah* (LMA), develop a more effective model, and assess perceptions of this new model among teachers and madrasah managers. The research adopted Borg and Gall's model, streamlined into three phases: preliminary, development, and evaluation. Data were gathered through observations and interviews at MA Pembangunan UIN Jakarta and MA UIN Yogyakarta. The development process included internal validation using the Delphi technique with inputs from educational experts and teachers, followed by external testing through preliminary and second stage tests at the aforementioned institutions. Findings revealed that the existing LMA management is overly centralized, with the director dictating policies and the principal handling only administrative duties. **Results:** The newly developed LMA model, aligning with National Education Standards and newly developed Cultural Standards, received a positive evaluation from teachers and managers, scoring an average perception rating of 4.03 (good). **Conclusion:** Its implementation significantly improved planning, organization, execution, and monitoring processes, proving that a stakeholder-focused approach in LMA management aligns well with Indonesian educational standards.

Keywords: Development Model, Laboratory, *Madrasah Aliyah*, Management Model.

INTRODUCTION

Madrasah Aliyah (MA) is a secondary education level in formal education in Indonesia, equivalent to Senior High School, which is managed by the Ministry of Religious Affairs (Refina et al., 2024; Juhaidi et al., 2024; Kusumaputri et al., 2023). *Madrasah Aliyah* (MA) as part of the national education, is currently required to be able to conduct education according to national education standards in Indonesia (Latief et al., 2021). The curriculum at *Madrasah Aliyah* emphasizes Islamic religious education as an addition to the general subjects, as is the case with SMA (Senior High School) in general. The challenges faced by MA are commonly related to management, standards of quality, teacher standards, prospective teacher quality, infrastructure, and curriculum. According to Sulaiman Syah (2016), prospective teachers must be innovative in facing global problems. The teachers should have a good data system and network. Therefore, Faculties of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training at Islamic Colleges, Islamic Institutions for Educational Personnel in Indonesia, are responsible for generating competent prospective Islamic education teachers. Furthermore, it is

crucial to improve the quality of madrasah management as it is a means of generating a generation possessing competencies in science and technology as well as Islam knowledge that characterizes madrasah education (Kusnanto et al., 2023).

As Islamic institutions, those universities are obliged to equip students in the field of education to be ready to become professional teachers in their fields. This is following paragraph 1, article 5 of Law number 12/2012 concerning higher education in Indonesia, stating that higher education aims to develop the potential of students to become people with faith and fear of God Almighty and moral people, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, skilled, competent, and cultured for the benefit of the nation. Students as prospective educators must master pedagogical, professional, personal, and social competencies. They must be trained in a systematic and measured manner. Teachers' competency requires current and continuous professional development (Sancar et al., 2021). Introduction, Connection, Application, Reflection, and Extension (ICARE) is a program designed to develop teachers' competency.

Laboratory is an important element and one of the requirements for a college. In Article 41 of Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education in Republic of Indonesia, universities must provide facilities and infrastructure to meet educational needs regarding students' talents, potential, and intelligence. Therefore, Laboratory schools function as a place for study, developing new practices, research and investigation, preschool education, as well as secondary education (Alam, 2024). Laboratory *Madrasah Aliyah* is a form of collaboration among State Islamic Universities (PTKIN), including State Islamic University (UIN), State Islamic Religion Institute (IAIN), State Islamic Religion College (STAIN), and partner schools (lab school) LMA. Compared to MA in general, LMA is better managed. Partnerships with universities are supposed to improve LMA quality, including reinforcing the clusters of MA diversification. Directorate of Madrasah Education of the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia divides madrasah into 4 models to develop and improve the quality of MA. They are academic madrasahs, vocational madrasahs, religious madrasahs, and regular madrasahs (Rahman et al., 2023).

Laboratory school is originated from John Dewey's experiment in 1896. It was triggered by his rejection of conventional educational models which at that time prioritized drills and rote learning. In his opinion, the teachers at that time had never received training in educational theories and methodologies in a real situation. (Kahne et al., 2022). In addition, according to Nielsen in April Blakely (2009), a laboratory school is designed as a facility affiliated with the higher education institutions in which the school is located. The main mission of a laboratory school is training teachers and creating a pedagogy. The main idea of LMA is to integrate and implement the results of educational research conducted by lecturers of religious universities and develop educational professions (Asrial et al., 2019). In line with the Winarni (2013) states that a laboratory school/madrasah is managed by a university or other teacher education institutions and is used for teacher training in the future, educational experiments, educational research, and professional development. However, the problem is that not all PTKIN have and optimize the existence of laboratory madrasahs as part of the PTKIN vision. Even if it does have a madrasah, how the madrasah is managed is questionable. Argues that madrasah should be headed by a professional, have teachers possessing superior personal competence, and students who are both physically and mentally intelligent (Ahmad & Salamun, 2017).

One of the factors that causes the low quality of madrasas, i.e. quality management, particularly the education manager or madrasah principle. He determines the quality of madrasah education. Low interest in MA is caused by intrinsic and extrinsic factors. The intrinsic factor is related to the limited facilities and infrastructure, while the extrinsic factor is due to the public trust. Most people think that senior high schools are better established than MA (Nurhamzah, 2016; Martani, 2023; Megawati et al., 2023). Furthermore, according to (Darling-hammond 2010), one of the problems in teacher training is conducting teaching practices. The management model referred to in this study is LMA management including planning, organization, implementation, and control. The development stage includes the National Education Standards and the added culture standard of LMA. This study aims to (1) investigate the currently implemented LMA management, (2) develop a LMA management model, (3) investigate teacher perception and madrasah managers toward LMA management model being developed, and (4) examine the results of implementing the developed LMA management model.

METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to develop a management model for laboratory madrasahs so that laboratory madrasahs can truly be the center of teacher professional development, education clinic, and top MA. In the process of developing a good management model for LMA, the researchers needed to investigate how the laboratory madrasahs conducted their duties and functions. Thus, this was a qualitative study as the researchers were involved in the laboratory madrasah management. This study tried to examine phenomena that occur in LMA and to find an effective management model for developing and improving LMA.

This research employed Borg and Gall's (2007) research and development model with ten stages which were simplified into three models, namely preliminary, development, and evaluation (Aka, 2019; Alfalah, 2023). The data were collected through observation and in-depth interviews in MA Pembangunan UIN Jakarta and LMA of UIN Yogyakarta. The model went through two stages, namely internal and external stages. The internal stage was conducted using the Delphi technique validated by four experts, one madrasah director, two madrasah principals, and five LMA teachers. The external testing was done through two steps, namely preliminary and second stage tests. The former was conducted in MA Pembangunan UIN Jakarta, and the latter was done in LMA UIN Yogyakarta. This qualitative study focused on the process as in Creswell (2018) states that qualitative research investigates people's lives, experiences, behaviors, emotions, and feelings, and so does an organizational function.

The *madrasah* management model implemented in this study may become a reference that contains procedures including planning, organizing, mobilizing, and supervising for the development and improvement of the quality of LMA. The planning process is done by the LMA principal and the director of *Madrasah Pembangunan*. This team must plan various *madrasah* activities after conducting need assessment so that programs in accordance with the needs are designed. Meanwhile, the organizing process in this study is done through discussions between the director of LMA and LMA management to develop an organizational structure.

Figure 1: LMA Management Model Organization

At last, in LMA management, supervision is conducted after the program is completed at the end of the academic year. The supervision is done by the monitoring and evaluation team selected by the LMA director.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current management model of the LMA is entirely determined by the director who is as well a lecturer at the university. The concept of Islamic management is now widely implemented in madrasahs in order to make madrasah management more effective. Effective madrasah management carries out program planning effectively, do the work plans effectively, and monitor and evaluate effectively (El Widdah, 2022). The *madrasah* principals tend to become implementers of the management policies made by LMA determined by the directors. Although this management model tends to be more stable, it shows the laboratory *madrasahs* do not receive any university policies regarding the implementation of the result of studies to improve teacher performance and learning processes. Besides, prospective teachers need to observe, conduct teaching practices, and research. Moreover, laboratory *madrasah* can be the place to improve their professionalism, personality, as well as pedagogical and social competencies. The developed and validated management model for LMA is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Developed LMA Management Model after Expert Validation

Experts and practitioners validating this study suggest that the management model should be more applicable, thus revision is made as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Applicable LMA Management Model

The effective management model for LMA is implemented following the needs of stakeholders by considering the National Education Standards (SNP) and developing cultural standards as a characteristic of LMA. An example of culture standard implementation is the Islamic education laboratory. The functions of LMA are presented below.

- a. Planning; designing LMA starting from the socialization and instilling of the concepts of Islamic education and science and technology to management, teachers, and staff; setting the image of LMA that can compete with other *madrassas* in terms of management; providing good service and developing trustworthiness and honesty; planning the application of an LMA management model; and network planning/establishing MOU with other parties.
- b. Organizing; The Head of LMA is an education practitioner, educational personnel should be a combination of teachers and administrators or professionals. Thus, the management of LMA is more focused. The work structure consists of the principal of *madrrasah*, vice-principal of academic and student affairs, finance staff, and teachers.
- c. Implementation; Socialization of correct LMA management to *madrrasah* heads, teachers and LMA managers, including: (1) Islamic and professional learning needs qualified teaching staff, thoughts, time, and funds. (2) LMA must function as a base of Islam education and other competencies in the field of education.

d. Supervision; Supervision is carried out in systematic and structured ways by internal and external parties. Internal parties are the *madrasah* principals, while the external parties are the city/district education office, the provincial education office, and the directorate of the MA Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. There is a need to apply clear operational supervision standards.

e. Human Resources; The management staff is professionals with certain skills.

The mean value of the perception of teachers and *madrasah* managers towards the management model of the developed LMA is 4.03 which belongs to the good category. The mean scores of the nine aspects being developed are presented in the following.

a. The Mean value of the content standard aspect is 4.16 (good)

b. The Mean value of the process standard aspect is 4.02 (good)

c. The Mean value of the aspect of graduate competence standard is 4.09 (good)

d. The Mean value of the aspect of teacher and educational personnel competence standard is 3.95 (good)

e. The Mean value of the aspect of infrastructure and facility standard is 3.87 (good)

f. The mean value of the aspect of management standard is 4.04 (good)

g. The mean value of the aspect of funding standard is 4.07 (good)

h. The mean value of the aspect of educational evaluation standard is 4.10 (good)

i. The mean value of the aspect of culture standard is 4.04 (good)

The implementation of the developed LMA management model at MA *Pembangunan* of UIN Jakarta and MA of UIN Yogyakarta show significant developments in terms of planning, national education standards, and human resources. Implementation in certain *madrasah* shows that the level of *madrasah* readiness will determine the success of LMA. Laboratory *Madrasah Aliyah* works together and partners with professional institutions. Financial aspects in the management of LMA are following national education standards in Indonesia. It is seen that the budget is recorded effectively and efficiently daily, monthly, or annually. The effectiveness of the management of LMA can be seen from the clear objectives, practical strategies, practical steps, and simple operations. This is manifested in a systematic, clear, and simple SOP for the development of the model LMA. The level of efficiency is represented by professional/Islamic human resources and good infrastructure. The professional aspect of labor emphasizes a good division of work and is following the job description, as well as the optimum use of infrastructure and attractive space design that makes the LMA more attractive. In addition, the quality of LMA management will result in significant changes in the orientation of the management of the LMA. The development of *madrasah* management must be based on National Education Standards to produce the LMA culture standards.

CONCLUSION

The developed management model of LMA is the final product that needs to be applied in all MA with the support of policymakers as well as the Ministry of Religious Affairs. This is evident that the development of the LMA has been able to generate Islamic graduates who possess knowledge of science and technology. Madrasahs should be

able to implement the developed management model to build students' excellent Islamic characters. Besides, LMA should become the model of Islamic education that is based on science and technology as well as the national education standards. This model may help instill the culture of Islamic education and science and technology in madrasahs. The Directorate General of Islamic Education of the Ministry of Religious Affairs should provide regulations for managing LMA following the results of this study.

Research on the development of the LMA management model needs to be done and disseminated through socialization and discussion with LMA managers. In addition, training for teachers and education staff working as the LMA management should be held to train the professional management staff of Islamic schools. Thus, Islamic characters can become the basis of building educational networks among madrasahs. The management model of the LMA can be developed for other Madrasahs. As LMA needs integrated managerial skills, a synergy of all LMA managers should be in place.

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